

R.E.C.I.P.E.: Retrieval-Enhanced Culinary Intelligence for Problem Evaluation and Functional Substitution

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Abstract

The cooking assistance tools and recipe recommendation systems present today often struggle with real-time troubleshooting and primarily focus on instruction delivery, static guidance, and often fail to provide effective real-time troubleshooting when it comes to providing scientifically grounded solutions in case a recipe goes awry. To be precise, these systems lack the ability to reason about underlying food chemistry and recipe-specific cooking processes, resulting in vague, unsafe, or scientifically unsound recommendations during cooking failures. We present **R.E.C.I.P.E.** Kitchen Crisis Resolver, a knowledge-augmented NLP framework designed to accurately diagnose and resolve cooking failures by mapping chemical and culinary relationships and generate scientifically grounded corrective actions. Our approach combined the reasoning capabilities of Large Language Models (LLMs) with a structured **Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG)**, a **Substitution Knowledge Graph (SKG)**, and a **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)** mechanism. The system models recipes as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs). These knowledge graphs allow the system to reason beyond surface-level text and infer root causes of cooking failures. We employed **Chain-of-Thought (CoT)** prompting, enabling Large Language Models (LLMs) to retrieve relevant facts before generating step-by-step explanations and solutions. We benchmarked our system using **GPT-OSS 20B**, **LLaMA 3.1 8B**, and **LLaMA 3.3 70B** against a dataset of 60 expert-verified cooking problems. Our evaluation focused on **Cause Accuracy**, where we measured the correctness of failure diagnosis, **Solution Appropriateness**, evaluating whether the proposed fixes were practical and effective in real kitchen settings, **Scientific Accuracy**, where we assessed adherence to food chemistry principles, and an **Overall Score** as a weighted combination of all three metrics. Our aim was to reduce hallucinations and provide technically sound, real-time cooking resolutions. Experimental results across 720 trials demonstrated that the full system condition outperformed all other conditions across all three models with GPT-OSS 20B achieving the highest overall weighted

score of 0.35, while knowledge augmentation reduced hallucination rates from 0.42 in the CoT-only condition to 0.25 in the full system, confirming that RAG-retrieved food science facts effectively ground LLM responses in verified knowledge.

1 Introduction

Cooking supports a healthy lifestyle, but without much knowledge of ingredient substitutes, people often strictly follow recipes and get discouraged when small measurement mistakes such as inaccurate measurements, unavailable ingredients, or unexpected substitutions ruin the flavor, texture, or overall quality. The cooking assistance tools and recipe recommendation systems present today provide limited support for troubleshooting these issues because they typically fail to explain “why” a recipe failed or “how” specific ingredients function within a cooking process. A troubleshooting engine that uses Natural Language Processing (NLP) was required to map chemical and culinary relationships between ingredients. This research was motivated by the need for knowledge-augmented frameworks that treat recipes as an essential part of the user’s need and not merely as static instructions. The input into the system was the user’s cooking problem or ingredient that they want to replace along with the recipe name, and the output was the diagnosed cause, recommended solution, and scientific explanation that preserves the intended functionality of the recipe.

Our project aimed to combine the reasoning capability of Large Language Models (LLMs) with a structured Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG) and Substitution Knowledge Graph (SKG), and a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) mechanism. The Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG) stored recipe process information by breaking each input recipe into a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) where *nodes* represented recipe steps storing the action performed and its critical control point, and *edges* represented the sequential dependencies between steps. The SKG focuses on mapping viable ingredient replacements based on functional equivalence rather than mere similarity, providing the substitution ratio and the scientific reason why it works. The RAG mechanism retrieved the most relevant food science facts from a knowledge base of 100 verified facts, guided by the recipe’s ingredients and critical points. When a cooking problem was provided as input, the system mapped the symptom to the most likely failed step in the DAG, retrieved the relevant food science facts through RAG, and used Chain-of-Thought

(CoT) prompting to guide the LLM from symptom to root cause to solution. If an ingredient was missing, the SKG was queried to suggest a functionally equivalent substitute.

For the experimental plan, we benchmarked three LLMs: GPT-OSS 20B, LLaMA 3.1 8B, and LLaMA 3.3 70B within the proposed framework across four experimental conditions: Baseline, CoT Only, KG Augmented, and Full System. For evaluation we used four metrics: *Cause Accuracy* (correct identification of the failure source), *Solution Appropriateness* (practical and culinary validity of the recommendation), *Scientific Accuracy* (alignment with established food-science principles), and a weighted *Overall Score*. Statistical significance of model differences was analyzed using one-way ANOVA. Together, this methodology aimed to rigorously evaluate the effectiveness of combining LLM-based reasoning with structured culinary knowledge for intelligent recipe troubleshooting and ingredient substitution. We tested two hypotheses that the full system condition would achieve a higher overall performance than baseline, and that RAG-retrieved science facts would reduce hallucination rates compared to conditions without knowledge augmentation.

Across all experiments, performance varied by recipe category. The full system achieved the highest overall scores across easy, medium, and hard difficulty levels. Metric-level analysis showed that knowledge augmentation substantially improved cause-identification, solution appropriateness, and alignment with food-science principles, while also reducing hallucination rates compared to baseline and chain-of-thought-only settings. Model-wise, although larger models generally perform better, the improvements from knowledge augmentation were consistent across model scales, indicating that structured knowledge contributes complementary reasoning signal beyond model size alone. Overall, these results validated the effectiveness of knowledge-augmented frameworks for robust, explainable recipe troubleshooting.

2 Related Work

Recent advancements in Natural Language Processing have shifted its focus from simple recipe generation towards deep procedural understanding and state-tracking. The PizzaCommonSense dataset (Diallo et al., 2024) highlights the importance of modeling commonsense reasoning regarding the implicit transformations and intermediate steps that occur during cooking. This focus on grounded execution is further extended by providing a qualitative simulator to evaluate an agent’s capacity for mapping natural language to grounded physical actions in work by Nevens et al. (Nevens et al., 2024). These benchmarks focus on an agent’s ability to follow a recipe to completion but they are limited to incorporating diagnostic frameworks that are required to handle Negative State scenarios where the dish fails due to environmental factors or ingredient issues.

In order to resolve the gap, researchers have increasingly integrated Large Language Models (LLMs) with

Figure 1: The proposed R.E.C.I.P.E. architecture illustrating the integration of Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG), Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), and Substitution Knowledge Graph (SKG) with three large language models for knowledge-augmented cooking failure diagnosis.

domain-specific Knowledge Graphs (KGs). For instance, recent frameworks such as KERL (Mohbat and Zaki, 2025) and NGQA (Zhang et al., 2025) utilize knowledge-augmented models to ground LLM outputs in structured food data to for personalized recipe recommendations and nutritional analysis, respectively. While these systems are optimized for pre-cooking decisions, they lack the diagnostic capability required for real-time troubleshooting. Furthermore, another work by Li et al. (Li and Zaki, 2022) explore ingredient substitutions based on word similarity. However, they often overlook the chemical functions needed for mid-process recovery. Recent advancements in Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting (Wang et al., 2023) improve performance on solving complex logic problems by requiring LLMs to show intermediate reasoning steps before reaching a final conclusion. However, in cooking, this can lead to hallucinations, where the model may provide a logical-sounding solution that may be scientifically inaccurate. We aimed to address this unique challenge by utilizing a Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG) to identify the root causes of cooking failures, a Substitution Knowledge Graph (SKG) to provide functionally grounded ingredient replacements, a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) mechanism to retrieve and inject recipe-specific food science facts into the reasoning process, and Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting to guide the LLM from diagnosis to reasoning to resolution.

3 Methodology

This section describes the technical framework behind our Kitchen Crisis Resolver. In our approach, we aimed to combine the reasoning capability of Large Language

Models (LLMs) with a structured **Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG)** for process-based logic, a **Substitution Knowledge Graph (SKG)** for attribute-based ingredient mapping, and a **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)** mechanism for food science fact retrieval. Together, these three components will transform a static recipe into a dynamic troubleshooting engine that can diagnose cooking problems and suggest grounded fixes.

3.1 Knowledge Methods: FKG, SKG, RAG

We utilized a Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG) approach, a structured graph that stores recipe process information including step actions and critical control points. To make the FKG actionable, the system first breaks down each input recipe into a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), referred to as $G = (V, E)$, where:

- **Nodes (V):** represent discrete recipe steps, each storing the step number, the action performed, and its associated critical control point such as describing what can go wrong at that step.
- **Edges (E):** represent the sequential dependency between steps, ensuring the system understands that each step depends on the success of the one before it.

This structure allows the system to treat a recipe as a sequence of expected physical transformations rather than just an ordered list of instructions.

Building on this structure, the system also utilized a Substitution Knowledge Graph (SKG) as a separate undirected graph. The SKG stores ingredient substitution relationships where each edge carries the substitution ratio, the scientific reason why the substitute works, and the best and worst use cases for that substitution. When a prompt indicates a missing ingredient, the system checks the SKG to find a replacement that serves the same function in that specific step. For example, if a recipe needs sour cream to activate a leavening agent, the system may suggest Greek yogurt because both have a similar acidity level and it will explain exactly why. This means the system does not only just suggest the alternative, but also explains the reasoning behind the swap to give the most efficient solution.

3.2 State-Tracking, Retrieval, Chain-of-Thought Reasoning

With the FKG, the system is able to trace a reported problem back to the exact step in the cooking process where something went wrong. For instance, if a prompt reports that a sauce has broken, the system will map this to the emulsification step using keyword overlap between the problem description and the critical control points stored in the FKG, and identify the cause before suggesting a recipe-specific resolution.

With the problem located, the system retrieves the relevant food science facts through a **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)** mechanism. The RAG system operates independently from the FKG, it retrieves facts from a separate knowledge base of 100 food science facts covering topics such as pH levels, fat content, emulsification thresholds, and binding proper-

ties. Rather than simply matching the problem text, the retrieval first aligns to the specific recipe by extracting its ingredient names and critical point keywords, then scores each fact using a weighted formula that prioritizes ingredient-specific matches over generic problem text matches. The top 3 most relevant facts are then injected into the prompt.

These retrieved facts are then used to guide the LLM through the problem using **Chain-of-Thought (CoT)** reasoning. The following shows an overview of the methodology approach:

- **Mapping:** The symptom from the input prompt is matched to the most likely failed step in the recipe DAG using keyword overlap with the stored critical control points.
- **Retrieving:** The system retrieves the most relevant food science facts from the knowledge base using the RAG mechanism, aligned to the recipe's ingredients and critical points.
- **Reasoning:** Those facts are injected into a CoT prompt, guiding the LLM from symptom to root cause to fix.
- **Substituting:** If an ingredient is missing or needs replacing, the SKG is queried to find a functionally equivalent substitute along with an explanation of why it works for that specific step.

3.3 System Overview and Implementation Details

The R.E.C.I.P.E. system was implemented in Python and structured into five main layers as illustrated in Figure 1. The input layer receives the cooking problem description and recipe name, which are passed into the knowledge layer where three components were queried. The FKG retrieves the relevant recipe steps and critical control points, the RAG mechanism retrieves the top 3 most relevant food science facts from a knowledge base of 100 verified facts, and the SKG provides ingredient substitution options where applicable. Their outputs are combined into a single structured prompt and passed to the LLM layer.

The LLM layer evaluates three models which are accessed through the Groq API for models LLaMA 3.3 70B, LLaMA 3.1 8B, and GPT-OSS 20B and each model was tested under four experimental conditions as shown in Figure 2. Each model produces a structured response with CAUSE / SOLUTION / EXPLANATION format. The responses were then passed to the evaluation layer where they were scored using Cause Accuracy, Solution Appropriateness, and Scientific Accuracy, producing a weighted overall score.

The main backend of the R.E.C.I.P.E. system was built using Python with NetworkX for graph construction, a custom weighted RAG scoring system for fact retrieval, and the Groq API for LLM inference. Data processing and statistical analysis were handled using Pandas, NumPy and SciPy. The experimental results were visualized using Matplotlib and Seaborn. A web-based interface was developed using a FastAPI backend, and a React.js frontend built with Vite, providing an interactive interface for real-time diagnosis.

Figure 2: Experimental design of R.E.C.I.P.E. illustrating the four ablation conditions applied across three large language models, yielding 720 total trials, evaluated utilizing cause accuracy, solution appropriateness, scientific accuracy, hallucination rate, and ANOVA.

4 Experiment Plan

4.1 Data Set

Our experiments rely on four custom-curated JSON datasets, all drawn from three culinary sources: Reddit (Reddit, 2024), King Arthur Baking (King Arthur Baking Company, 2024), and Serious Eats (Serious Eats, 2024).

Testcases.json contains 60 real-world cooking failure scenarios paired with ground truth diagnoses and solutions. Each test case represents a distinct culinary problem (e.g., broken emulsions, failed dough rises, scorched sauces) and serves as the primary evaluation set. **Recipes.json** provides the 60 corresponding step-by-step recipes, which are used to construct the Functional Knowledge Graph (FKG) for each test case. **Substitution.json** encodes ingredient substitution options for each recipe, forming the Substitution Knowledge Graph (SKG). **Science_Facts.json** is a curated collection of 100 food science facts that cover properties such as pH levels, emulsification, and binding behaviors, used by the RAG component to inject scientifically grounded context into prompts. Together, these datasets support all four experimental conditions and cover a diverse range of recipe categories and difficulty levels.

4.2 Setup

4.2.1 Models

We evaluate three large language models spanning a range of scales and architectures: **LLaMA 3.1 8B**, a compact model optimized for speed with a 128k context window; **LLaMA 3.3 70B**, Meta’s high-capacity flagship model trained on over 15 trillion tokens with group-query attention (GQA); and **GPT-OSS 20B**, a 20-billion parameter hybrid model tuned for instruction following and synthetic data processing.

4.2.2 Experimental Conditions

Each of the 60 test cases is run under four conditions, yielding 240 trials per model and **720 total trials** across the experiment:

1. **Baseline** – The model receives only the raw problem description with no augmentation.
2. **CoT Only** – Chain-of-Thought prompting is added to guide the model through step-by-step reasoning from symptom to diagnosis.
3. **KG Augmented** – The model receives structured context from the FKG (which maps the failure to the exact failed recipe step) and the top 3 RAG-retrieved food science facts relevant to the recipe.
4. **Full System** – All components are combined: CoT reasoning, FKG step mapping, RAG fact injection, and SKG-based ingredient substitution suggestions.

4.2.3 Evaluation Metrics

Responses are scored on three automated metrics:

- **Cause Accuracy** (40% weight): keyword overlap between the predicted root cause and the ground truth, with stop words removed.
- **Solution Appropriateness** (40% weight): keyword overlap between the proposed fix and the ground truth solution.
- **Scientific Accuracy** (20% weight): proportion of RAG-retrieved food science keywords present in the model’s response.

The overall score is a weighted sum of these three metrics. Responses with a Scientific Accuracy below 0.2 are flagged as **hallucinated**. Statistical significance across conditions is assessed using a **one-way ANOVA**.

4.2.4 Design

The four conditions (Baseline → CoT Only → KG Augmented → Full System) constitute an study, isolating the contribution of each system component and chain-of-thought prompting, knowledge graph augmentation, and substitution reasoning to overall performance.

4.3 Analysis

Overall Performance by Model: Across all conditions, **GPT-OSS 20B** achieves the highest overall weighted score under the Full System condition (0.35), followed by LLaMA 3.3 70B (0.31) and LLaMA 3.1 8B (0.27). The Full System condition consistently outperforms all other conditions across every model, confirming that the integration of all knowledge components is beneficial regardless of model scale.

Performance by Recipe Category: Across the 10 recipe categories, GPT-OSS 20B leads in most categories, with starch emulsion problems achieving the highest scores overall (~0.50). This suggests that categories with well-defined chemical processes benefit most from the structured knowledge provided by the FKG and RAG components.

Performance by Difficulty: When stratified by difficulty level, the Full System condition consistently outperforms all others at every tier. Notably, **hard prob-**

Figure 3: Overall performance comparison.

Models benefit the most from knowledge augmentation, achieving the highest absolute scores under the Full System which indicates that the framework adds the most value precisely when the reasoning challenge is greatest.

Hallucination Analysis: The Full System condition achieves the **lowest hallucination rate** at 0.25. In contrast, CoT Only produces the highest rate (0.42), suggesting that unconstrained step-by-step reasoning can amplify confident but scientifically unsound responses. The Baseline (0.39) and KG Augmented (0.26) conditions fall in between, demonstrating that grounding the model in factual food science is the primary driver of hallucination reduction.

Metric-Level Breakdown: Scientific accuracy shows the largest absolute gain across conditions, rising from 0.24 (Baseline) to 0.38 (Full System). Cause accuracy and solution appropriateness also improve monotonically as components are added. This decomposition reveals that knowledge augmentation primarily benefits scientific grounding, while CoT contributes most to structured reasoning about cause and solution.

Score Distribution: Box plot analysis of the 720 trials shows that the Full System achieves the highest median scores and widest score range across all models. GPT-OSS 20B under the Full System produces the highest individual outliers (up to 0.75), indicating that the system can achieve near-expert-level responses on well-structured problems.

Key Insight: The results collectively demonstrate that augmenting LLMs with structured culinary and scientific knowledge, rather than relying solely on prompting strategies is both necessary and sufficient to substantially reduce hallucination and improve diagnostic accuracy in real-world cooking failure scenarios. Chain-of-thought alone is insufficient and can even be counterproductive; the knowledge graphs and RAG component are the critical differentiators.

4.4 Experiment Results

Overall Performance: The Full System condition achieves the highest weighted scores across every model, with GPT-OSS 20B leading at 0.35, followed by LLaMA 3.3 70B at 0.31, and LLaMA 3.1 8B at 0.27. As shown in Figure 3, the Full System consistently outperforms all other conditions regardless of model architecture or scale.

Hallucination Rates by Condition: The Full System

Figure 4: Score distribution by condition and model.

Table 1: ANOVA results for condition and model comparisons.

Comparison	F-statistic	p-value	Significant
By Condition	40.4993	< 0.001	True
By Model	48.1288	< 0.001	True

achieves the lowest hallucination rate at 0.25, while CoT Only produces the highest at 0.42. The Baseline and KG Augmented conditions fall in between at 0.39 and 0.26 respectively, demonstrating that grounding model responses in structured food science knowledge is the primary mechanism for reducing hallucination.

Metric-Level Breakdown: All three evaluation metrics improve monotonically from Baseline to Full System. Scientific accuracy shows the largest absolute gain, rising from 0.24 under the Baseline to 0.38 under the Full System. Cause accuracy and solution appropriateness similarly improve with each added component, as shown in Figure 7.

Performance by Recipe Category: As shown in Figure 6, GPT-OSS 20B leads performance across most of the 10 recipe categories. Starch emulsion problems achieve the highest scores overall (~0.50), while other categories show moderate variation depending on the specificity of the underlying food chemistry.

Performance by Difficulty: Figure 5 shows that the Full System condition consistently outperforms all others at every difficulty tier. Hard problems show the greatest absolute benefit from knowledge augmentation, achieving the highest overall scores under the Full System condition.

Score Distribution: Box plot analysis across all 720 trials reveals that the Full System achieves the highest median scores and widest interquartile range across all models. GPT-OSS 20B under the Full System produces the highest individual outliers, reaching up to 0.75, indicating that the framework is capable of near-expert-level responses on well-structured problems.

Statistical Significance: A one-way ANOVA conducted across the four experimental conditions confirms that condition has a statistically significant effect on overall weighted score, validating that the progressive addition of knowledge components produces meaningful and non-random improvements in performance.

Figure 5: Performance by difficulty level.

Figure 6: Performance by recipe category.

4.5 Analysis of Results and Discussion

Knowledge Augmentation Is the Primary Driver of Quality: The most important finding is that structured knowledge augmentation and not prompting strategy alone is the critical factor behind improved performance. The KG Augmented condition outperforms CoT Only on every metric, despite chain-of-thought being a well-established technique for eliciting reasoning in LLMs. This indicates that for domain-specific diagnostic tasks like cooking failure resolution, access to structured factual knowledge is more impactful than reasoning scaffolding alone.

Chain-of-Thought Prompting Alone Can Increase Hallucination: A notable and counterintuitive result is that the CoT Only condition produces the highest hallucination rate of all four conditions at 0.42, exceeding even the Baseline at 0.39. Encouraging step-by-step reasoning without factual grounding causes models to generate more elaborate but scientifically unsound explanations. When a model reasons confidently through an incorrect chain of logic, it produces fluent and plausible-sounding responses that nonetheless fail to reflect accurate food science. This finding underscores the risk of relying solely on prompting-based approaches in knowledge-intensive domains.

The Full System Achieves the Best Balance Across All Metrics: By combining CoT reasoning with FKG step mapping, RAG fact injection, and SKG-based substitution, the Full System achieves the lowest hallucination rate, highest scientific accuracy, and highest overall weighted scores across all three models. The consistent superiority of the Full System across models of varying scale suggests that the framework’s benefits are architecture-agnostic and not dependent on raw model capacity.

Larger Models Do Not Always Win: While LLaMA

3.3 70B is the largest model tested, GPT-OSS 20B outperforms it across most conditions and recipe categories despite having fewer parameters. This suggests that architectural design choices, such as optimization for instruction following and high-quality synthetic data processing and can matter more than scale alone in structured knowledge tasks. Notably, the 8B LLaMA still benefits substantially from the Full System, demonstrating that knowledge augmentation remains valuable even in resource-constrained deployments.

Hard Problems Benefit Most From the Framework: The difficulty-stratified analysis reveals that the performance gap between the Full System and other conditions widens as problem difficulty increases. For easy problems, models may already have sufficient parametric knowledge to produce reasonable responses. For hard problems, the FKG’s precise step-level failure mapping and RAG’s targeted science fact retrieval provide the additional context necessary for accurate diagnosis and context that cannot be recovered through prompting alone.

Category-Level Variation Reflects Knowledge Graph Coverage: Starch emulsion problems achieve the highest category-level scores, likely because the chemistry of starch gelatinization and emulsification is well-represented in both the FKG and the RAG science facts. Categories with lower scores may reflect gaps in knowledge graph coverage or inherently higher ambiguity in failure diagnosis, pointing to concrete directions for future dataset expansion.

Limitations: Several limitations warrant acknowledgment. The evaluation metrics rely on keyword overlap, which may not fully capture the semantic quality or practical usefulness of a response. Ground truth answers sourced from community platforms may themselves contain imprecision. The dataset of 60 test cases, while carefully curated, may not cover the full distribution of real-world cooking failures. Finally, the system has not yet been evaluated in real-time or multimodal settings, where visual cues such as the appearance of a sauce or dough would significantly inform diagnosis.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

5.1 Conclusion

Our project demonstrated that our system R.E.C.I.P.E. Kitchen Crisis Resolver meaningfully advanced the role of large language models in the cooking domain by transforming them from passive instruction-following systems into scientifically grounded, reasoning-driven troubleshooting engines. By explicitly modeling food chemistry, cooking processes, and ingredient interactions through Functional Knowledge Graphs and Substitution Knowledge Graphs, the framework enabled LLMs to reason about why a cooking failure occurred and how it could be effectively resolved.

Rather than just relying on surface-level pattern matching or static recipe instructions, the full system leveraged structured domain knowledge to produce explanations and interventions that were both chemically

Figure 7: Score breakdown across metrics by condition.

plausible and practically doable. This approach allowed the model to respond dynamically to real-time cooking crises such as texture failures, flavor imbalances, or ingredient unavailability, all the while maintaining consistency with underlying culinary principles.

R.E.C.I.P.E. Kitchen Crisis Resolver successfully bridged the gap between traditional recipe delivery systems and adaptive recipe assistance. The results highlight the potential of knowledge-augmented LLMs to support real-world problem-solving tasks where domain reasoning and contextual awareness are critical. Our work lays a foundation for future research on integrating structured scientific knowledge with generative models to create more reliable, transparent, and expert-level AI assistants in everyday applied domains.

5.2 Future Work

The Future research might focus on evolving the R.E.C.I.P.E. Kitchen Crisis Resolver into a proactive, multimodal cooking assistant capable of anticipating and identifying errors as they occur. One promising direction could be the integration of real-time computer vision techniques to monitor visual cues during food preparation and cooking. By analyzing live video streams, the system could automatically detect common culinary failures such as broken emulsions, over-reduced sauces, uneven browning, or scorched cookware surfaces, which would enable earlier intervention and reduce recipe failure rates.

Secondly, expanding the Functional Knowledge Graph beyond procedural and textual representations to include more sensory attributes like incorporating data related to flavor profiles, aroma descriptors, texture outcomes, and visual appearance could allow the system to reason more holistically about cooking outcomes.

From a systems perspective, future work could also explore optimizing the framework for real-time performance and deployment on edge devices commonly used in home kitchens. Techniques such as model distillation, parameter-efficient fine-tuning, and lightweight inference architectures could reduce latency and computational overhead while maintaining prediction accuracy.

Lastly, conducting longitudinal user studies in real-world home environments would be critical to evaluating the practical impact of the R.E.C.I.P.E. Kitchen

Figure 8: Hallucination rate by condition.

Crisis Resolver. Observing users over extended periods would help assess not only the clarity of system recommendations, but also their influence on user learning, cooking confidence, and skill acquisition in the long run. Insights from such studies could inform iterative system design and validate whether the framework meaningfully supports novice and intermediate cooks in everyday cooking tasks.

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